

PREPARATION OF ARYLAMIDES OF 2-METHOXY-, 4-METHOXY- AND
2-HYDROXY- 4-METHOXY-BENZOIC ACIDS

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Several arylamides of 2-methoxy-, 4-methoxy- and 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-benzoic acids have been prepared by condensing the acid chloride with the amines in presence of pyridine or PCl_5 .

A few arylamides of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoic acid, and of 2- and 4-methoxy-benzoic acids have been prepared by the interaction of the acid and the amine in presence of phosphorus trichloride or pyridine.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Methoxybenzoyl chloride was prepared by boiling the acid (10 g.) in dry toluene (30 c.c.) with thionyl chloride (10 c.c.) for about 8 hours and removing toluene and excess of thionyl chloride by distillation. The crude acid chloride was mixed with the requisite amine (12 g.) in presence of pyridine (10 c.c.), and the mixture was left over at room temperature for about 15 minutes. The mixture was then first triturated with HCl (dilute) and then with a dilute solution of NaOH. The compounds obtained were crystallised from suitable solvents in yields of nearly 65% (Table I).

TABLE I
[A represents 2-methoxybenz-]

Amides.	Cryst. from.	Cryst. appearance.	M. P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
A-anilide	Chloroform + pet. ether	Colorless needles	74-75°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	6.3	6.2
A-o-toluidide	EtOH	„ plates	89-90°	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$	5.8	5.8
A-m- „	Dil. alcohol	„ needles	74-75°	„	6.0	5.8
A-p- „	Do	Do	62-66°	„	6.1	5.8
			(distils at 205-206°/ 0.75 mm)			
A-o-nitroanilide	Acetic acid	Pale yellow needles	133-34°	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$	10.6	10.3
A-m- „	Benzene	Do	139-40°	„	10.0	10.3
A-p- „	Acetic acid	Yellow soft needles	170-71°	„	10.2	10.3
A-p-anisidide	Dil. EtOH	Colorless prisms	73-74°	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_3\text{N}$	5.7	5.5
A-p-phenetidide	EtOH	„ rect. plates	94-95°	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_3\text{N}$	5.5	5.2

* It was prepared by Haller (*Compt. rend.*, 1895, 121, 189; Beilstein, XII, p. 501) by heating the acid with phenyl isocyanate. He recorded m.p. 62°.

The arylamides of 4-methoxybenzoic acid were prepared in the same way as those of 2-methoxy isomer (Table II). The yields were about 65%.

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TABLE II

[B represents 4-methoxybenz-]

Amides.	Cryst. from.	Cryst. appearance.	M.P.	Formula	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
B- <i>o</i> -toluidide	EtOH	Colorless needles	161-62°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N	6.0	5.3
B- <i>m</i> - "	Dil. EtOH	Do	107-108°	"	6.0	5.8
B- <i>p</i> - "	Acetic acid	" rect. plates	153-54°	"	6.1	5.8
B- <i>o</i> -nitroanilide	Benzene + pet. ether	Yellow needles	114-15°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₂	10.5	10.3
B- <i>o</i> -anisidide	dil. MeOH	Colorless needles	95-96°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	5.8	5.5
* B- <i>p</i> - "	EtOH	" leaflets	202-203°	"	5.5	5.5
B- <i>p</i> -phenetidide	Acetic acid	" needles	174-75°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₃ N	5.5	5.2
† B-β-naphthyl- amide	Benzene	" "	179-80°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₂ N	5.3	5.0

* Schnackeneberg and Scholl (*Ber.*, 1903, 36, 654) prepared this compound by Beckmann's transformation.

† The crude product was washed with dilute acetic acid instead of dilute hydrochloric acid as in other cases.

The amides of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenzoic acid were prepared by heating on a boiling water-bath for 4 hours the acid (5 g.) with the amine (10 g.) in presence of phosphorous trichloride (1.5 c.c.) and then diluting the mixture and working up the product in the same way as in the previous two cases, the only difference being that sodium bicarbonate was used in place of sodium hydroxide. These are described in Table III. The yields were about 30%.

TABLE III

[C represents 2-hydroxy-4-methoxybenz-]

Amides.	Cryst. from.	Cryst. appearance.	M. P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
C-anilide	EtOH	Colorless granules	157-58°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N	6.0	5.8
C- <i>o</i> -toluidide	"	" needles	143-44°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	5.7	5.4
C- <i>m</i> - "	"	" "	141-42°	"	5.3	5.4
C- <i>p</i> - "	Benzene	" rhombic plates	151-52°	"	5.5	5.4
C- <i>o</i> -nitroanilide	Acetic acid	Yellow needles	144-45°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₂	9.6	9.7
C- <i>m</i> - "	"	Colorless needles	194-95°	"	10.0	9.7
C- <i>p</i> - "	"	Pale yellow plates	223-24°	"	9.8	9.7
* C- <i>o</i> -anisidide	Dil. MeOH	Colorless needles	100-101°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ N	5.3	5.1
C- <i>p</i> - "	Acetic acid	" "	164-65°	"	5.2	5.1
C- <i>p</i> -phenetidide	Chloroform + pet. ether	" lustrous cubes	151-52°	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₄ N	4.8	4.9
‡ C-β-naphthylamide	Benzene	" cubes	174-75°	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N	4.9	4.8

* The reaction mixture in this case was heated at 120° to get the product in better yields.

‡ The crude product was washed with dilute acetic acid instead of dil. HCl as in other cases.